

OXIDATIVE STRESS OF INDIVIDUALS PRACTICING PHYSICAL ACTIVITY

Irakli Chaganava^{1,2} - Associate Professor, PhD in chemistry (chaganava@irakli.info);

¹Georgian State Teaching University of Physical Education and Sport, Tbilisi, Georgia;

²Institute of Cybernetics of Georgian Technical University, Tbilisi, Georgia.

Abstract. This paper provides a brief overview of some the most accepted scientific findings from the field of oxidative stress research. The report is made taking into account sports specifics. The issue at hand is still under consideration and the evidence regarding oxidative stress continues to come in rather slowly, especially in the context of individuals who practice physical activity. The phenomenon itself from a chemical point of view is ambiguous. For example, even one agent, interacting in the organism with various biochemical substances, is able to conduct separate chains of transformations in parallel (Figure 1). Despite the fact that the end substances and histological pathologies observed as a result of oxidative stress have been identified, the mechanism of their development remains controversial in a quantity of aspects. Circumstances of this kind hinders both the effective prevention of undesirable consequences and the search for means to recover from the harm caused by the considered pathological biochemical process. It should be emphasized that when offering ways to solve this issue by both pharmacological and nutritional means, the neutralization of hyperoxidative processes should not be so regular that it would affect normal oxidative processes, including the formation of peroxides. It should not be assumed that the use of antioxidants, in any case, will be harmless. Thus, the solution of the issue under consideration is recommended to be carried out in a complex manner, taking into account quantitative regulation, and not a blind struggle at a qualitative level against oxidative processes, including those leading to the formation of reactive oxygen species, peroxides and free radicals normally used by organisms in physiologically required limited quantities.

Keywords: reactive radical particles, oxidative stress, antioxidants, physical exercise.

Introduction. Oxidative stress (OS) per se is a metabolic shift in equilibrium in favor of stressors that promote the formation of free radicals. The latter are known for their high chemical activity and, in case of weakening of compensatory mechanisms, cause damage to tissues, accelerating the aging of the body and creating conditions for the occurrence of some serious diseases. It should be noted that as a result of studying the factors leading to this kind of health threat, among other things, the occurrence of oxidative stress during intense physical exertion against the background of an unfavorable antioxidant status of a person practicing sports activity has been scientifically confirmed. Many studies have shown that exercise induces oxidative stress and on the other hand stimulates adaptations in antioxidant defenses.

Materials and methods. To monitor the OS process, researchers are mainly guided by the indicator of the compensatory mechanism of the so-called antioxidant status. This parameter is especially important in restorative and sports medicine. Researchers have identified biochemical markers that occur during oxidative stress. Markers of OS are the following indicators: leukocytosis simultaneously with an increase in the level of isoprostane in the urine, substances active in relation to thiobarbituric acid, including protein carbonyls and catalases, as well as the formation of glutathione peroxidase and / or oxidized glutathione, and separately the percentage of oxidized glutathione to its reduced form. For monitoring, observations of the level of advanced oxidation

protein products (AOPP) and malondialdehyde (MDA) are taken, as for example, following up the antioxidant status is conducted with a marker known as ImAnOx.

Results and discussions. In the process of studying research publications devoted to the effect of oxidative stress on the organism of an athlete, the authors most often indicate a particularly undesirable consequence known as lipid peroxidation. According to the observations of most researchers, the intensity of formation of this class of substances is proportional to the increase in the proportion of loads of speed-strength orientation. The probability of formation of fatty acid peroxides reaches its maximum in the competitive period of the athlete's training.

Figure 1. Mechanism of free radical toxicity (credits: Dan Cojocari, Princess Margaret Cancer Centre, University of Toronto).

It should be noted that biochemical reactions, including lipid peroxidation, are the norm and physiologically necessary to ensure the proper functioning of cell membranes, as well as important processes associated with energy metabolism and intracellular signaling. Fat

peroxidation should be considered harmful if it occurs in excess, which, however, occurs quite often. There is a popular opinion among scientists that the increase in the level of lipid peroxides associated with the intensity of physical activity is due to a decrease in the bioavailability of nitric oxide (NO), which is an important regulating biochemical agent of oxidative processes. However, for example, a German group of researchers does not agree with this explanation of the reason for this observation and clarifies the mechanism of oxidative stress, which is not associated, for example, with the formation of nitric oxide from arginine. Moreover, their works indicate the beneficial effect of this substance on the tolerance of high-intensity exercise. The most significant criterion for the principal conclusions of researchers is the state of health of the studied individuals, which indirectly or directly affects the antioxidant status of an athlete. However, a healthy body can also end up with an unfavorable antioxidant status as a result of prolonged aerobic endurance training, which, according to the research team of Jirakarit Leelarungrayub (from Chiang Mai University, Thailand), can lead to damage to body tissues by oxidative stress.

Researchers come to the conclusion that in some cases, the loss of the target effect of training may be due to dysfunction of protease systems, which, in an environment of oxygen deficiency, exacerbates metabolic disorders, causes suppression of the activity of certain enzymes, disrupts the conjugation of oxidation and phosphorylation processes and develops other toxic effects that lead to overtraining and decline in athletic performance and undermine a healthy metabolism. Correction of the consequences of temporary oxygen deficiency is usually carried out by general cryotherapy, inhalation of a gas mixture rich in oxygen; if helium is included in the mixture, oxygen absorption is further improved.

Attention is required to exercise of excessive duration or high-intensity ones, in which prompt compensation of substances excreted with sweat is required. In case of lack of replenishment and loss of fluid is in the amount of 2% of body weight, the most likely disruption of the flow of physiological processes occurs, especially those responsible for performance. The importance of rehydration is noted to minimize stress on the cardiovascular, thermoregulatory and neuromuscular systems. Although many researchers demonstrate in detail the relationship between physical exercises and hydration processes, the question of the effect of rehydration on oxidative stress remains unclear, nevertheless, it definitely exists. The authors of the sports literature report a vicious circle of the emergence and self-sustaining of pathology, the stages of which are as follows: oxygen deficiency disrupts the athlete's energy metabolism and induces free radical oxidation, which in turn leads to damage to mitochondrial membranes and redoubles energy deficiency in the cell, which ultimately leads at best, to a decrease in efficiency, and at worst facilitates the development of formidable diseases by pathophysiological processes in conditions of a depressed immune system.

Conclusion

It has been repeatedly confirmed that with an excessive increase in the level of free radicals, unfavorable conditions for the organism arise, leading to harm to DNA molecules and related diseases. In addition to the damage to the genetic material, an excess fraction of free radicals negatively affects health due to the occurrence of pathophysiological processes from a much wider spectrum, which contributes to the development of health problems such as cardiovascular diseases associated with degeneration of brain tissue and the occurrence of autoimmune pathologies. A number of studies come to the consensus that increased aerobic exercise is associated with oxidative stress and tissue damage, but the mechanisms of this process still need

to be clarified in order to improve the efficiency of managing this phenomenon, which is still the subject of discussion. Regarding the issues among which the least doubt remains is the recommendation of the competent use of antioxidants, the baseless consumption of which can lead to problems of the same nature, which they try to avoid by using antioxidants.

The development of preventive measures against the harm of oxidative stress will be much more effective in research on supporting internal compensatory mechanisms and ensuring their harmonious functioning than direct counteraction to oxidative processes.

References:

1. Cases N, Sureda A, Maestre I, Tauler P, Aguiló A, Córdova A, Roche E, Tur JA, Pons A. Response of antioxidant defences to oxidative stress induced by prolonged exercise: antioxidant enzyme gene expression in lymphocytes. *Eur J Appl Physiol.* 2006; 98(3): 263-269.
2. Dreißigacker U, Wendt M, Wittke T, Tsikas D, Maassen N. Positive correlation between plasma nitrite and performance during high-intensive exercise but not oxidative stress in healthy men. *Nitric Oxide.* 2010;23(2):128-135. doi: 10.1016/j.niox.2010.05.003
3. Hadžović-Džuvo A, Valjevac A, Lepara O, Pjanić S, Hadžimuratović A, Mekić A. Oxidative stress status in elite athletes engaged in different sport disciplines. *Bosn J Basic Med Sci.* 2014;14(2):56-62. doi:10.17305/bjbms.2014.2262
4. Ji L. Oxidative stress during exercise: Implication of antioxidant nutrients. *Free Radical Biology and Medicine.* 1995;18(6):1079-1086. doi:10.1016/0891-5849(94)00212-3
5. Leelarungrayub D, Saidee K, Pothongsunun P, Pratanaphon S, YanKai A, Bloomer RJ. Six weeks of aerobic dance exercise improves blood oxidative stress status and increases interleukin-2 in previously sedentary women. *Journal of Bodywork and Movement Therapies.* 2011;15(3):355-362. doi: 10.1016/j.jbmt.2010.03.006
6. Tauler P, Sureda A, Cases N, Aguiló A, Rodríguez-Marroyo JA, Villa G, Tur JA, Pons A. Increased lymphocyte antioxidant defences in response to exhaustive exercise do not prevent oxidative damage. *J Nutr Biochem.* 2006; 17(10): 665-671.